

Terrain Modeling in 3D Mapping for Autonomous Navigation in Multi-layered Environments

Jan Bayer^[0000–0003–1190–1085] and Jan Faigl^[0000–0002–6193–0792]

Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague,
Technická, 2, 166 27, Prague, Czechia
{bayerja1,faiglj}@fel.cvut.cz
<https://comrob.fel.cvut.cz>

Abstract. In this paper, we propose precise geometrical terrain modeling for autonomous navigation of mobile ground robots. Terrain’s geometrical features, such as elevation, roughness, and slope, are essential for terrain traversability estimation to support planning safe and efficient paths through the robot’s operational environment. Elevation 2.5D maps are suitable for traversability assessment and can profit from a high vertical resolution; however, 3D map representation is needed when operating in environments with multiple terrain layers. Vertical voxelization is utilized in existing OctoMap and UFOMap at the cost of relatively low vertical resolution induced by the voxelization, which might lead to a false assessment of terrain traversability. Therefore, we propose a novel method that combines the advantages of 3D maps with a high vertical resolution of terrain modeling. The benefits of the solution are demonstrated in three scenarios: tunnel, indoor passage, and outdoor terrain, where the proposed method outperforms existing map approaches. Besides, the impact of proposed terrain modeling is demonstrated in practical planning examples for ground mobile robots.

1 Introduction

In the context of autonomous navigation and exploration [14] or reconnaissance [12], the precision in the vertical direction of the environment model is not a critical parameter for office-like indoor environments with flat floors and obstacles that are easy to identify. However, for mobile robots deployed in uneven terrains, tunnels, and multilayer infrastructure [3], a full 3D representation of the terrain model is needed. Moreover, when robots with low ground clearance are used on uneven terrains, it is crucial to have a precise estimation of the terrain shape, allowing correct traversability assessment.

Existing 3D map representations, such as the OctoMap [8], capture a 3D scene at a specific voxel resolution equal in both vertical and horizontal directions. The low resolution of the grid map is beneficial for the planning since there are fewer states to be searched by the planner, and the low resolution also

Fig. 1. A visualization of the proposed map representation of the 3D environment. The size of the map’s voxels is 16 cm, which can be seen for the horizontal directions, although the voxel size in vertical direction is 16 cm as well, the voxelization is hardly recognizable in vertical direction, since z-coordinates of the rendered cubes correspond to filtered height measurements, stored in each voxel.

benefits sensory noise reduction. On the other hand, a high vertical resolution of the terrain representation is essential for calculating geometrical terrain features to determine step height and roughness, which are essential for traversability assessment [18].

We propose to combine the existing 3D mapping approach with an adjustable horizontal resolution and a high vertical resolution suitable for traversability estimation. Contrary to existing methods such as the OctoMap, which increases resolution at the cost of dense voxelization, the high vertical resolution is achieved by combining the map with terrain height estimation inspired by elevation mapping techniques. An example of the visualized 3D map of the proposed representation is shown in Fig. 1. Two main contributions of the presented work are as follows.

- Map representation capable of representing 3D data more precisely than existing 3D grid maps by avoiding voxelization in the vertical direction;
- Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the voxelization impact on traversability estimation and planning.

The paper is organized as follows. An overview of the existing map representations and related traversability estimation methods is provided in Section 2.

The studied problem is specified in Section 3. The proposed map representation and its primary usage for traversability estimation are presented in Section 4. Evaluation results are reported in Section 5, and concluding remarks are summarized in Section 6.

2 Related Work

The main motivation of the presented work is geometrical terrain modeling for traversability estimation in autonomous navigation. Direct detection of geometrical features for traversability estimation and negative obstacles, respectively, from the LiDAR scans are utilized in [9,10]. The authors of [6] use the robot-centric elevation map to fuse multiple scans from the sensors and thus handle the sensory noise and increase the area covered by the robot’s sensors. The elevation mapping is also used in [18], where the authors infer the traversability from the geometrical model by calculating slope, roughness, and step height. The same geometrical properties of the terrain model are used in the hybrid approach [11], where the geometrical model is combined with the semantic segmentation of RGB images to improve traversability estimation.

The computation of the terrain slope is studied in [20] by taking into account the suspension model of the vehicle and thresholding vehicle tilt angles in the lateral and longitudinal directions. Besides the tilt angles, the authors compute roughness and step height from the point clouds to evaluate the traversability. The same geometrical features are combined with learning in [13] to learn the traversability cost as a measure of how difficult it is to traverse various surfaces.

Elevation mapping is used in the methods mentioned above to aggregate data from the sensors and provide representation suitable for the traversability estimation. The elevation maps are suitable, especially due to their high vertical resolution, which supports precise calculation of terrain step height and terrain roughness. Although the elevation mapping is well suited for traversability estimation, it is not sufficient for multi-layered environments. Existing 3D map representations include the OctoMap [8] that represents an environment with hierarchically organized voxels, each measuring the occupancy probability. The main disadvantage of the OctoMap is demanding access to the spatial data, albeit it is memory efficient. That is why the authors of [4] proposed UFOMap with improved memory management using an explicit representation of the occupied, free, and unknown states in the map.

Both the OctoMap and UFOMap divide the space into voxels, where the selected voxel size defines the vertical resolution. The voxel size directly impacts planning, as for a larger voxel, planning is faster because fewer states need to be searched. However, it is at the cost of less precise traversability estimation due to a low vertical resolution. On the other hand, when the voxel size is decreased to make traversability estimation more precise, the map access times increase, and sensory noise is less reduced.

In the proposed approach, we aim to address the limitations of the low vertical resolutions of the full 3D maps by including surface elevation information

to make them usable for precise traversability estimation while keeping independently selectable horizontal resolutions, which can be adjusted based on the target environment and planning requirements. The proposed representation is compared with voxel-based 3D map representation using a precision of the representation defined in the following section.

3 Problem Statement

The addressed problem is to create a 3D map environment representation that stores a given area as precisely as possible. In particular, we are focused on the vertical resolutions that are important for calculating geometrical terrain features, such as the step height and roughness, for the traversability estimation. Besides, it is also desirable to have quick access to the spatial information to use the map for planning autonomous navigation during the mission, as in the DARPA Subterranean Challenge [1], where the representation is accessed frequently as a part of the online decision-making in the exploration task [2]. In the present work, the precision of the representation is evaluated by the average \bar{e}_m and standard deviation σ_m of the absolute map error defined as

$$\bar{e}_m = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{r}_i\|, \quad \sigma_m = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{r}_i\|^2}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{r}_i is a 3D point uniformly sampled from the map representation under the test, and \mathbf{q}_i is the 3D point of the reference point cloud that is the closest reference point to \mathbf{r}_i .

4 Method

The proposed map representation has been designed to be deployed in autonomous or semi-autonomous robotic scenarios such as autonomous exploration, patrolling, and assisted teleoperation, which put stress on the trade-off between the achievable map precision and computational requirements. However, it can be deployed in purely mapping applications, where the access demands might not be as high as in online decision-making. Therefore, we describe the mapping framework, traversability assessment, and planning to demonstrate the full potential of the proposed map representation in navigation scenarios.

4.1 3D Mapping

The input to the mapping is a sequence of 3D point clouds obtained from a range sensor(s), such as RGB-D cameras, LiDARs, or even Total stations. It is presumed that the input point clouds are already aligned to the coordinate frame of the map representation, for example, using Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) techniques, such as LOAM [19], or LIO-SAM [16], to name a

few. The new points of the input data are fused with the existing map using the following procedure.

First, the occupancy probability $p_{occ}(n)$ is updated for all the cells incident with a ray cast from the center of the sensor to the position of the obtained measurement. Next, for the voxel (cell) n that corresponds with the end of the ray, the estimation of the terrain surface's height is updated. The estimation is done incrementally by a one-dimensional Kalman filter, which is already utilized in elevation mapping [5,17]. The new measurement of the surface height, measured as the z coordinate of the point that is updating a cell n and its variance $\sigma_{z,k}^2$ generated by the linear sensor model, is fused with the current estimate of the height $h_{k-1}(n)$ and its variance stored in the cell n by

$$h_k(n) = \frac{\sigma_{z,k}^2 h_{k-1}(n) + \sigma_{h,k-1}^2(n) z_k}{\sigma_{z,k}^2 + \sigma_{h,k-1}^2(n)}, \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{h,k}^2(n) = \frac{\sigma_{z,k}^2 \sigma_{h,k-1}^2(n)}{\sigma_{z,k}^2 + \sigma_{h,k-1}^2(n)}, \quad (3)$$

where $h_{k-1}(n)$ and $\sigma_{h,k}^2(n)$ are the updated estimates, stored in the cell n , of the terrain height and its variance, respectively.

The proposed map uses an octree representation similar to the OctoMap [8]. When the output of the map representation is requested, the selected part of the map representation is searched for the occupied cells. Thus, cells with the state $state(n) = occupied$ are searched based on the occupancy probability $p_{occ}(n)$ with the state defined as

$$state(n) \begin{cases} unknown & t_f \leq p_{occ}(n) \leq t_o \\ occupied & t_o < p_{occ}(n) \\ free & t_f > p_{occ}(n) \end{cases}. \quad (4)$$

The confidence levels t_f and t_o allow for setting when a cell switches its state from unknown to free or occupied.

4.2 Traversability Estimation

The traversability is estimated based on the step height [18] that is defined as the maximum difference between the neighboring map cells that belong to the terrain surface. Thus, the traversability is set to infinity for cells that do not belong to the terrain surface. The surface cell is identified as an occupied map cell n with the height $h(n)$ only if there is no occupied cell m with the height $h(m)$, where $h(n) \leq h(m) \leq h(n) + r_h$ and r_h is the height of the robot.

The traversability $t(n)$ of the surface cell n is computed based on the maximum height difference between the cell n and its neighbors as

$$d(n) = \max(h(n_i) | n_i \in 8nb(n))$$

$$t(n) \begin{cases} m_t \cdot d(n) & d(n) < r_t \\ \infty & r_t \leq d(n) \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

where $8nb(n)$ is the 8-neighborhood of the cell n , providing for each of 8 columns the surface cell, closest to n . r_t is the maximum height of the step traversable by the robot, and m_t is the traversability scale for the final adjustment of the traversability to be in line with the map resolution.

In the last step of traversability computation, we follow the cost map approach [15], and the resulting geometrical traversability is generated by applying distance transform [7] generalized to 3D on $t(n)$.

4.3 Path Planning

The proposed map representation with the evaluated traversability is employed in path planning as follows. A path for the vehicle is generated by projecting start and goal locations to the surface of the corresponding 3D map representation. Then, A* planner is used to search neighboring surface cells while taking into account the estimated traversability $t(n)$ so that the edge between two neighboring map cells is evaluated by higher traversability associated with the two cells.

5 Results

Two test scenarios are designed to evaluate the precision of the proposed map representation and its usability in autonomous navigation. In the first test scenario, the absolute map error (1) is computed for the proposed and reference map representations. In the second scenario, we showcase the proposed map representation in the planning scenario.

5.1 Quantitative Evaluation of the Mapping Precision

Three different environments were scanned to evaluate the map precision of the selected reference OctoMap [8] and the proposed map representation. For both map representations, we have set the voxel size to 10 cm, and the thresholds for the occupancy probability to consider a cell is a free space and obstacle are set to $t_f = 0.4$ and $t_o = 0.6$, respectively. The environments used for testing are a cave tunnel approximately 600 m long, an office-like indoor environment, and the outdoor area at the Czech Technical University in Prague, campus at Charles’s Square, Prague, Czechia, see Fig. 2.

The reference map of all three environments is created using the 3D laser scanner Leica BLK360 with centimeter precision. Each scan was fed into the map representations under the test. Then, the point cloud representing the environment has been rendered from both map representations. The absolute map error according to (1) is employed to measure the precision of the rendered maps with respect to the original scan of the environment. The achieved results are summarized in Table 1.

The results presented in Table 1 show that the proposed map representation always has a slightly lower absolute error than the OctoMap approach. The

Fig. 2. Visualization of the 3D point cloud maps used to evaluate the map representation.

Table 1. The absolute map error for the map representations.

Trial	OctoMap [8]		Proposed	
	\bar{e}_m [cm]	σ_m [cm]	\bar{e}_m [cm]	σ_m [cm]
Cave tunnel	4.74	1.46	3.88	1.56
Indoor area	3.45	1.80	2.49	1.74
Outdoor area	4.52	1.57	3.87	1.57

standard deviations of the absolute error are similar for both methods. The cost paid for the increased map precision is a more demanding memory footprint of the proposed map representation. The data structures used to build the map representations are shown in Table 2. If the OctoMap is considered with the complete trees, based on the data structures described in Table 2, the proposed map representation has approximately about 47% larger memory requirements.

Table 2. Map representation data structures.

Node	OctoMap		Proposed	
	Content	Size [B]	Content	Size [B]
Connect	8 Successors	64	8 Successors	64
Leaf	Probability	4	Probability	4
	traversability	4	Traversability	4
			Height	4
			Height variance	4

5.2 Planning using the Proposed Geometrical Model

The proposed and reference OctoMap map representations have been examined in the following planning scenario. The scan of the outdoor environment, as shown in Fig. 2c, is fed to both map representations. Next, the traversability estimation, described in Section 4.2, has been employed to identify traversable and untraversable areas for a small wheeled robot. It is assumed that the wheeled robot is the Clearpath Jackal with 65 mm ground clearance; thus, $r_t = 0.065$. The estimated traversability for both methods under the test is visualized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Visualization of the environment representations with the resolution 16 cm and traversability assessment, where the increasing traversability cost is from red to blue.

From Fig. 3, it can be seen that the proposed map representation provides improved estimates of the surface shape than the OctoMap, in which the corresponding is marked as untraversable, indicated by the blue cells. Thus, the geometrical traversability based on the proposed map representation captures different difficulties of the terrain surface for the used vehicle, which is not captured by the OctoMap. The way the traversability affects the planning is further illustrated in Fig. 4. The same traversability model used with a different map representation yields different path avoiding rough terrain.

The main advantage of the proposed mapping approach is that it reduces the fluctuation of the terrain height. For the existing standard mapping approach represented by the OctoMap, the terrain height estimation fluctuates at some places due to the imprecise point cloud alignment or disagreement between the real sensor parameters and the sensor model. The fluctuation generates changes in the terrain height at least equal to the map resolution, and some cells change their state between occupied and free or occupied and unknown. On the other hand, for the proposed map representation, the vertically neighboring cells agree on an estimate of the surface height with an error lower than the map resolution.

Fig. 4. Visualization of the map representation with the resolution 16 cm used in the planning test scenario. The planned path is visualized in the magenta color. The initial robot locations are marked as red spheres in a blue circle.

6 Conclusion

We present a method to increase the vertical resolution of the 3D map representation and thus support terrain traversability assessment. Although the proposed method requires approximately about 47% more memory than the OctoMap in the evaluated scenarios, there is a slight improvement in the map precision. The absolute map error induced by the proposed map representation is about 14.4% up to 37.8% lower than the error induced by the OctoMap representation in three different scenarios that include cave tunnel, indoor area, and outdoor area. The proposed map representation thus enables improved precision of the geometrical terrain traversability estimation, which is especially important for ground vehicles with low ground clearance. Moreover, we demonstrate that increased vertical resolution can significantly impact path planning with the terrain traversability estimated from the geometrical terrain model. When the planner uses the estimated traversability based on the proposed map representation, it better distinguishes terrain parts that can be traversed by the robot and the cost of doing so than the reference method.

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